
SYNONYMS IN A LITERARY TEXT (IN THE EXAMPLE OF TURA SULAYMON'S WORK)

Khayrulla Khamdamovich Ibragimov¹

Mukaddas Turopova²

Jizzakh branch of National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek

KEYWORDS

Emotional coloring, tone, stylistics, neutral, art, support, cousin, brother's wife, salt, black, lonely, beloved, honor, conscience, if, but

ABSTRACT

The most important of the linguistic features of a literary text is that it includes emotionally colored words, dialect words, historical and archaic words, slang and slang words, figurative words, synonyms, forms, words with similar pronunciations and opposite meanings, as well as units such as phrases, proverbs and sayings are wide given. This article focuses on one of Tura Sulaymon's main tools for ensuring the diversity of artistic discourse, the ability to use synonyms as an important means of expression in language.

2181-2675/© 2024 in XALQARO TADQIQOT LLC.

DOI: **10.5281/zenodo.11911716**

This is an open access article under the Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/deed.ru>)

¹ Ph.D., Associate Professor, Jizzakh branch of National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek, Uzbekistan

² Teacher of school 47, Gallaorol district, Jizzakh region

Synonyms are one of the factors that indicate the richness and diversity of a language. Synonyms help to express an idea clearly and effectively. For this reason, word artists try to use them skillfully. The artist's artistic skill and vocabulary can be seen in the synonyms he uses appropriately and purposefully.

One of such creators, the poet Tura Sulaymon, also skillfully used synonyms. He used colorful synonyms in the vocabulary of the Uzbek language to discover new aesthetic concepts.

*Senga qolgan kunim, kunmas – qabohat,
Koshki sendan kutsam imdod, inoyat!
Meni qo'llay olur, qilur himoyat
Uzilmas torlarim,
Sinmas sozlarim! ("Sozim")*

The word "help" is synonymous with the words "help, support, help" and "means of material or spiritual support." In the word help, the strength of the shade is stronger than the word support, and is likely to be used in an artistic style. The poet perfects art using the words help, support, help, a synonym for help, which means grace instead of caring.

Tura Sulaymon also skillfully used dialectal words and contributed to their approval in the literary language.

*Holimdan kuladi necha-nechalar...
Bir yilcha tuyular o'tgan kechalar.
Har kuni xunobda yanga-chechalar...
Jumboqni boshidan o'tgan yecholar!
Do'stlaro, shu taqlid rozga yo'liqdim ("Yo'liqdim").*

The word khesh belongs to the dialect and means relative, kin-clan, tribe-relative, close person. The poet ensured the universality and fluency of his poem through the element of dialect.

*Qo'riqchisi bo'lardim bog'imda unar bo'lsa,
Kuzim kelmay bahorim qayta boshlanar bo'lsa,
Solnomachisi bo'lay magar u Qamar bo'lsa,
Qasam ichib aytaman: namak bir yon, non bir yon ("Gul bir yon, chaman bir yon").*

The poet uses the word salt, a synonym of the word salt used in dialect. Through this he put the poetic weight in its place.

Sound is a dialectal word from the synonymous series sound, sound, flour, echo, sas, outcry, sazo, and is used in fiction, especially in poetry.

*To'plar sasi bo'lmasin
Deymiz, sayyoramizda,
Biz – jahon bolalari ("Biz – jahon bolalari").*

*Tutdi mahalla-ko'yni qo'sh karnay, surnay sasi,
Sayoq sozandalarning ortiqcha dahmazasi.
Badmastlar orasida guzaron – tarafbozlik,
Isrof ustiga isrof to'yxonaga "jonbozlik" ("Sen so'rama, men aytmay").*

Tura Sulaymon always paid great attention to the fact that synonymous words are not absolutely equal to each other, each of them has its own characteristics and subtle differences in their meanings, and was able to use them in their place.

In the "Explanatory dictionary of synonyms of the Uzbek language" as a synonymous line of the word friend is given comrade, ulfat, agayni, oshna, jora, brother, hamdam, dugona, vascular, chopkat³. But their level of use and style are different. The words jora, brother, ulfat are less used than the words comrade, oshna, agayni. The lexical meaning of the word ulfat is consent, alliance, solidarity, and it means love, affection, and love. A conversation is a gathering of people who are always together at a banquet, a gathering of such people. In the poet's book of satirical poems, "I threw it away," he says that after giving up drinking, his friends left. The poet does not use the word friend in this context. Because in this word the intimacy in a friendly relationship is even stronger. No one can be a good friend.

*Bora-bora ulfatlar tashlab qochar ham bo'ldi,
Kaminangiz bedavo dardga duchor ham bo'ldi.
To'yxatlardan tamomi nomi o'char ham bo'ldi,
Qirqaqa yetmay qomat lol-xiyol nochor ham bo'ldi,
Tashlagandan tashladim ichib, cheqmoqlaringni ("Tashladim")*

In another verse of the same poem he now uses the word friend.

*Rangi ro'yimga, do'stlar, yugurdi qon, oqibat.
Tashlagandan tashladim ichib, cheqmoqlaringni ("Tashladim")*

In another poem on the same subject, he mentions the difference between a friend and a partner, quoting the word friend as well as the word partner.

*Do'st, sheriklarim alkashlar
Yurganda yo'li chalkashlar
"Kim bilan kim topishadi!"
Deb kulishar hazilkashlar ("Ichdim, armonim qolmadi").*

It is very important for the poet to take into account that "synonyms are not for the differentiation of semantic shades, but for the nature of the stylistic shades and emotional colors they express"⁴, which are always in touch with our emotions and emotional life. Tura Sulaymon did not ignore this aspect either.

The words darling, mahbuba, yor, nigor, dildor are used as synonyms for yor. But the lyrical protagonist uses the word sarvinozim, whose art is stronger than these words.

Ro'zg'orimdan to'zim ketdi,

³ Khojiev A. Annotated dictionary of synonyms of the Uzbek language. - Tashkent, 1974. - 310 p.

⁴ Quchqorto'ev I. Synonym words and some of their features. "Problems of Linguistics", Book 1. - Tashkent, 1960.

*Qo'radan qo'y-qo'zim ketdi. Bu kulfatga chidayolmay
Tashlab sarvinozim ketdi* ("Ichdim, armonim qolmadi").

The word beloved is a gender-specific lexeme. It applies equally to men and women. At this point, the poet uses the word boy in the girl's language with her friend. It is known that this word is peculiar to the oral style, and by this the creator showed the vitality of the theme, the idea of the poem.

*"O'z sevgan yigitim, sevgan yorim bor,
Dunyoga bergusiz nomus, orim bor* ("Alhazar").

These synonyms, which have an emotional and stylistic character, served to distinguish the subtleties of different meanings and to give color to the poem.

Poetic speech is speech that requires a concrete, artistic-figurative expression of the concept being expressed. In this process, the word plays an important role as a speech medium. Indeed, the fact that poetic speech is based on measurement and melody, solemnity, in many cases, prevents the replacement of a word used in the text with a synonym or equivalent of that word⁵. The poet Tura Sulaymon uses the word in such a way that the thought becomes clear, the essence is fully revealed. Grass is a synonym for the word greens, and is often used in dialects. Suman, on the other hand, is a white-flowered, fragrant plant that is used in an artistic style. The poet contrasts these two plants with each other, and for artistic purposes quotes one as a synonym for speech, one for artistic style.

*Birda naf, foyda deb kechamiz jondin,
Jonday do'st, e'tiqod, insof, imondin.
Farq qilmasdin birda rostni yolg'ondin,
Alaf bo'la bilmas
Sumandin ortiq* ("Ortiq")

The poet quotes synonymous words over and over again, increasing empathy, artistry, and emphasizing the idea he wants to express.

*Xohi rozi bo'lg'in, xohi norizo,
Xohi motam tutib, xohi och aza,
Dovrug'lari bo'lib elga ovoza,
Uzilmas torlarim,
Sinmas torlarim* ("Sozim")

The meanings of mourning and mourning are closely related verbs, and the poet has used them consistently to reinforce the meaning.

*Men uchun bu dunyoning ko'rkamligi sen bilan,
Bearmonu beafg'on, bekamligi sen bilan.
O'n sakkiz ming olamning olamligi sen bilan,
Bu jahonda ko'rmasin shahlo ko'zing hech yosh, qiz* ("Seningsiz").

⁵ Umirqulov B. Vocabulary of poetic speech. - Tashkent: Fan, 1990.

The words *bearmon*, *beafghon*, and *bekam* in these verses are meaningful, expressing the signs of a happy person and coming together to increase expressiveness. The word *Beafghan* is used in the bibliography style to mean no, no cry.

Bedov ot tuyog'idan tayrilarmi?

Mard yigit to'g'ri yo'ldan qayrilarmi?

Nomusi, oriyati bor yigitlar

Yori deb tuqqanidan ayrilarmi? ("Oqpadar")

In these verses, the words honor and dignity are combined, and it is emphasized that this blessing is very important for young men.

Indeed, lexical units cannot be said to be neutral to the language of poetry. Because poetic vocabulary, first, does not arise spontaneously. Language itself allows it to be stratified for poetic speech. In this sense, synonymy is a source of poetic word formation. Tura Sulaymon was able to make effective use of this rich source.

The poet also used the synonymy of auxiliary words in a way consistent with poetic discourse. Unless the conditioner connects, the opposition connector, however, has managed to reinforce the meaning of the condition in the poem by using the if form, which is characteristic of the artistic style:

Sayyoralar notinch, ummonlar notinch

Magar yer yuzida tinchlik bo'lmasa.

Naslu nasab notinch, zamonlar notinch

Magar yer yuzida tinchlik bo'lmasa ("Bo'lmasa").

The verse "Unless there is peace on earth" is repeated from beginning to end in this poem, emphasizing the importance of peace.

The poet skillfully used the *pianista* and *alkash* variants of his expression, which was given to alcohol with a negative color:

Yuz ketidan kaminaning

O'rni poygak – pastda bo'ldi.

Nomim pianista bo'ldi.

Bo'ldi, armonim qolmadi ("Ichdim armonim qolmadi").

Do'st, sheriklarim alkashlar

Yurganda yo'li chalkashlar.

"Kim bilan kim topishadi!"

Deb kulishar hazilkashlar ("Ichdim armonim qolmadi").

The poet was able to create a unique art and style, using synonyms appropriately and purposefully, one of the lexical units, which demonstrates the skill of language use, the emotional-expressive expressions of which are realized in a bubble.

Literature used

1. Ibragimov X. THE PEOPLE IN THE POETIC RISE OF TORA SOLOMON'S WORK THE PLACE OF PROVERBS // Архив Научных Публикаций JSPI. – 2020.

2. Ibragimov, X. (2022). Dars mashgulotlarining samaradorligini oshirishda yangi pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanish. Zamonaviy Innovatsion Tadqiqotlarning dolzarb muammolari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari: Yechimlar va istiqbollar, 1(1), 551–554. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/zitdmrt/article/view/5258>

3. Hamdamovich I. K. TURA SULAYMON'S SKILLS OF USING ANTONYMS //CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES (2767-3758). – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 03. – С. 71-75.

4. Ibragimov X. Tura Sulaymon ijodining poetik yuksalishi //Архив Научных Публикаций JSPI. – 2020.

5. Ibragimov, Xayrulla. (2021). ТЎРА СУЛАЙМОН ШЕЪРИЯТИДА МЕТАФОРАНИНГ ЎРНИ . FILOLOGIYA UFQLARI JURNALI, 4(4). извлечено от <https://hp.jdpu.uz/index.php/hp/article/view/2022>